

Bibliometric Analysis of Literature on SME Entrepreneurial Orientation Using VOSviewer Software.

Auteur 1 : ALLAMMARI Yassin

Auteur 2 : JARIDE Chama.

Auteur 3 : TAQI Ahmed.

Auteur 4 : EL AAROUBI Siraj.

ALLAMMARI Yassin, (PhD Student in economics and management), Management Finance Digitization and Applied Statistics Research Laboratory, Faculty of Legal, Economic, and Social Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tétouan, Morocco.

JARIDE Chama, (Ph.D. in economics and management), Management Finance Digitization and Applied Statistics Research Laboratory, Faculty of Legal, Economic, and Social Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tétouan, Morocco.

TAQI Ahmed, (Professor of Higher Education), Management Finance Digitization and Applied Statistics Research Laboratory, Faculty of Legal, Economic, and Social Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tétouan, Morocco.

EL AAROUBI Siraj, (Professor of Higher Education), Management Finance Digitization and Applied Statistics Research Laboratory, Faculty of Legal, Economic, and Social Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Tétouan, Morocco.

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Abstract

Entrepreneurial Orientation Has Become A Crucial Topic In Management And Entrepreneurship, As It Determines Smes' Ability To Innovate, Seize Opportunities, And Take Calculated Risks. This Managerial Practice Has Been Identified In Recent Literature As A Key Factor In Developing The Competitiveness And Performance Of Smes In Uncertain And Ever-Evolving Environments. Therefore, This Study Aims To Create Co-Citation Maps To Identify The Most Influential Articles And Term Networks To Understand The Main Concepts And Themes Addressed In The Literature On The Entrepreneurial Orientation Of Smes. To Achieve This, A Sample Of 415 Relevant Publications From The SCOPUS Database Was Analyzed Using Vosviewer Software To Extract The Bibliographic Data Required For Our Analysis. Our Results Reveal Some Interesting Findings. We Observe A Significant Growth In The Number Of Publications On This Topic Over Time, Reflecting The Increasing Interest In Entrepreneurial Orientation Within Smes. Furthermore, We Identify Key Authors, Journals, And Concepts That Dominate The Research Field. Finally, We Discuss The Implications Of Our Findings For Future Research In This Area And Suggest Avenues For Further Studies.

Keywords

Entrepreneurial Orientation, Bibliometric Analysis, Smes, Vosviewer, Scopus.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship Is Prominent In The Economic Landscape, Crucial In Job Creation, Economic Growth, And Innovation (ALLAMMARI Et Al., 2023). Within This Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Smes Are Particularly Important, Often Considered To Be The Driving Force Behind Innovation And Economic Dynamics In Many Countries (Sajjad Et Al., 2023; Saleh & Athari, 2023).

One Of The Essential Dimensions Of Smes' Strategic Orientations Is Their Entrepreneurial Orientation, Which Refers To: "*A Company's Propensity To Adopt Behaviors And Strategies Typical Of Entrepreneurs, Such As Innovation, Risk-Taking, And The Search For Growth Opportunities To Meet The Challenges Of Its Business Environment.*" (Covin & Slevin, 1989; Garcia & Calantone, 2002; Wang, 2008). Therefore, Understanding This Entrepreneurial Orientation Is Crucial To Understanding How Smes Function And Perform (Allammari, Jaride, Taqi, Et Al., 2024; Iyiola Et Al., 2023).

Against This Backdrop, The Academic Literature On SME Entrepreneurial Orientation Has Grown Exponentially In Recent Years (Allammari, Jaride, Azdod, Et Al., 2024; Anzules-Falcones & Novillo-Villegas, 2023). This Proliferation Of Publications Testifies To The Growing Interest Of Researchers In This Field And The Recognition Of Its Importance In Understanding The Entrepreneurial Behavior Of Smes (Zighan Et Al., 2022).

However, This Abundance Of Research Work Can Make It Complex To Synthesize Existing Knowledge And Understand Emerging Trends (ALLAMMARI Et Al., 2023; Iqbal Et Al., 2021). This Is Where Bibliometric Analysis Comes In, A Powerful Methodological Approach That Enables Academic Literature To Be Systematically Mapped, Visualized, And Analyzed (Merigó & Yang, 2017; Perianes-Rodriguez Et Al., 2016).

With This In Mind, This Study Aims To Carry Out An In-Depth Bibliometric Analysis Of The Literature On SME Entrepreneurial Orientation. We Will Rely On Vosviewer Software, Widely Recognized For Its Ability To Visualize Co-Citation And Co-Occurrence Networks Of Terms, In Order To Map Trends, Patterns, And Relationships Between Articles Published In This Field.

By Synthesizing And Reviewing Existing Literature, This Bibliometric Analysis Will Provide Valuable Insights Into The Most Influential Research, Emerging Trends And Gaps To Be Filled In The Understanding Of SME Entrepreneurial Orientation (Hina Et Al., 2021). These Insights Will Be Useful Both For Researchers Wishing To Contribute To This Field And For Practitioners Seeking To Develop Effective Strategies For Stimulating Entrepreneurship Within Smes.

In The Remainder Of This Article, We Present The Methodology Used To Carry Out Our Bibliometric Analysis, The Results Obtained, And The Implications Of Our Contributions For Future Research In This Field.

1. The Role Of Bibliometric Analysis

According To Schildt Et Al (2006, P.12), The Bibliometric Analysis Identifies Research Trends By Examining Publications And Analyzing Their Frequency And Evolution Over Time. It Also Identifies The Most Productive And Influential Authors And Institutions In A Given Field Of Research As Well As The Most Relevant And Frequently Cited Journals (Moral-Muñoz Et Al., 2020). It Also Offers The Opportunity To Analyze Collaboration Networks Between Researchers And Institutions, Which Can Help To Understand Research Dynamics And Identify Strategic Partnerships (Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015).

Finally, A Bibliometric Literature Review Identifies Gaps In The Existing Literature And Research Opportunities For New Studies, Highlighting Less Explored Areas Or Topics With Little Coverage (Donthu Et Al., 2021).

Thus, This Analysis Would Enable Us To Offer A Quantitative And Systematic Perspective On Research In The Field Of Entrepreneurial Guidance, Helping Us To Better Understand The Academic Literature And To Direct Future Research In A More Relevant And Targeted Way. Bibliometric Methodology Can Be Defined As A Set Of Techniques Aimed At Quantifying The Process Of Written Scientific Communication (Okubo, 1997). Indeed, When Carrying Out A Bibliometric Study, It Is Essential To Select Databases Wisely, Particularly With Regard To The Coverage Of Indexed Journals (Landström Et Al., 2012).

For This Study, The "*Scopus*" Database Was Chosen For Its Features Such As Daily Updating, Some 22,000 Titles From Over 5,000 International Publishers, And Statistical Analyses Enabling A Preliminary Assessment Of The Articles Identified. In Addition, This Database Also Classifies Studies According To Specific Fields Of Knowledge, Facilitating Navigation And Comparison. In Addition, Scopus Offers Three Citation Metrics, Including Scimago Journal Rank (SJR), Impact Per Publication (IPP), And Source Normalized Impact Per Paper (SNIP), Enabling Precise, Comparative Evaluation Of Scientific Journals.

2. Materials And Methods

3.1. Sample

To Conduct This Analysis, We Used The Term "Entrepreneurial Orientation". The Search Was Carried Out In The Titles, Abstracts, And Keywords Of The Publications. In Addition, The Study Of Articles Was Spread Over A 10-Year Period From 2013 To 2023 In Order To Map

All Recent Production In The Field Of Entrepreneurial Orientation. In Addition, No Language Restrictions Were Applied, But Selected Articles Had To Have Been Peer-Reviewed. The Research Process For This Bibliometric Study Is Described In Figure 1.

Figure 1. Bibliometric Survey Procedure

Source: Compiled By The Authors

Our Final Sample Consisted Of 415 Articles Published In Recent Years In The *Scopus Database*.

3.2. Analysis Methods Bibliometrics

To Analyze The 415 Articles In The Sample, Data Tables Were Prepared In Excel Spreadsheet Format And Imported Into The Sphinx Lexica® Software Used For Descriptive Statistical Analysis. Tables And Graphs Were Then Prepared To Map The Following Bibliometric Indicators:

- Scientific Output;
- Most Popular Scientific Journals;
- Countries With The Highest Production;
- Institutional Affiliation Of Researchers;
- Most Productive Authors;
- Most Cited Articles And Citation And Co-Citation Map;

- Main Subjects Studied.

For Citation And Co-Citation Analyses, The "*Vosviewer*" Software Was Used Following The Recommendations Of Eck & Waltman (2017) Which Enabled The Mapping Of The Most Cited Authors And The Articles Most Used As References In The Sample Texts, As Well As The Identification Of Key References And Coherent Co-Citation Networks On Which The Authors Based Their Research (ALSHARIF Et Al., 2020).

Next, A Similar Procedure Was Used To Analyze The Topics Studied In The OE Articles: Using Language Processing Techniques, *Vosviewer* Extracts Textual Terms And Creates A Map Indicating The Distance Between Them, Defined By The Level Of Co-Occurrence Of The Terms (Perianes-Rodriguez Et Al., 2016). In General, A Smaller Distance Between Two Terms Indicates A Higher Co-Occurrence Between Them. The Sum Of Occurrences Of A Term In The Titles And Abstracts Of The Articles Analyzed Was Also Calculated.

3. Result And Discussion

3.1. Descriptive Analysis

This Section Presents Data On The Evolution Of Scientific Production; The Scientific Journals In *Scopus* That Have Published The Most On The Subject; The Authors' Countries Of Origin And Institutional Affiliation. These Data Represent A Set Of Indicators For The Field And Can Generate "Big Picture" Views On EO As An Area Of Interest For Our Research.

3.2. Scientific Production

Analysis Of The Number Of Scientific Publications Per Year In The Field Of Entrepreneurial Orientation Is An Important Indicator Of Research Interest And Activity In This Area. The Following Table Shows The Number Of Articles Published On Entrepreneurial Orientation Each Year, Covering The Period Between 2013 And 2023 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number Of Documents Published By Year Between 2013 And 2023

Source: Compiled By Us From The Scopus Database

As The Figure Shows, The Number Of Publications Of Articles On Entrepreneurial Orientation Seems To Have Experienced An Upward Trend In Recent Years. In Particular, We Observe A Notable Increase Between 2013 And 2021, From 12 To 74 Articles. This Upward Trend Indicates A Growing Interest In This Topic Within The Academic Community. However, We Should Also Note A Slight Drop In The Number Of Articles Published In 2022 And 2023 Compared With The Previous Year, Although The Number Remains Relatively High.

3.3. Main Academic Journals Dealing With Entrepreneurial Orientation

The Following Table Shows The Top Ten Journals That Published Articles On Entrepreneurial Orientation, Ranked By The Number Of Articles Published And The Percentage Of The Total 415 Articles Analyzed (Table 1).

Table 1. Main Journals Publishing On Entrepreneurial Orientation Between 2013 And 2023

Ranking	Publication Journal	Number	%
1	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	134	32.28
2	INDUSTRIAL MARKETING MANAGEMENT	58	13.97
3	INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS REVIEW	30	7.22
4	TECHNOLOGICAL FORECASTING AND SOCIAL CHANGE	29	6.98
5	EUROPEAN MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	19	4.57
6	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS VENTURING	18	4.33
7	JOURNAL OF INNOVATION KNOWLEDGE	17	4.09
8	TECHNOVATION	16	3.85
9	JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL MANAGEMENT	15	3.61
10	JOURNAL OF WORLD BUSINESS	12	2.89
Total		348	83,85

Source: Compiled By Us From The Scopus Database

The 415 Articles In The Sample Were Published In 47 Journals, Just 10 Of Which Accounted For 83.85% (348 Articles) Of The Scientific Output Analyzed. At The Top Of The Ranking, The "Journal Of Business Research" Stands Out With 134 Articles Published, Representing Around 32.28% Of All Articles Published On The Subject Of Entrepreneurial Orientation. In Second Place, "Industrial Marketing Management" Has 58 Articles, Closely Followed By "International Business Review" With 30 Articles. These Data Show A Significant Concentration Of Published Articles On Entrepreneurial Orientation In A Small Number Of Journals, Underlining The Importance Of These Journals In The Field Of Entrepreneurial Orientation Research.

3.4. Country Of Publication

Table 2 Below Provides An Analysis Of The Top Ten Countries That Have Published On Entrepreneurial Orientation. The Data Includes The Number Of Articles Published By Each Country And The Corresponding Percentage Out Of A Total Of 415 Articles Analyzed.

Table 2. Main Countries That Have Published On Entrepreneurial Orientation

Country	Number Of Items	% Of 415
USA	105	25,30%
ENGLAND	74	17,83%
PEOPLES R CHINA	34	8,19%
GERMANY	25	6,02%
SPAIN	24	5,78%
FINLAND	20	4,82%
AUSTRALIA	17	4,10%
FRANCE	17	4,10%
ITALY	13	3,13%
India	12	2,89%
Total	341	82,17%

Source: Compiled By Us From The Scopus Database

The Table Shows That The USA Leads The Way With 105 Articles Published, Representing Around 25.30% Of The Total Number Of Articles On Entrepreneurial Orientation. In Second Place Is England With 74 Articles, Followed By The People's Republic Of China With 34. Together, These Three Countries Account For More Than Half (51.32%) Of All Articles Analyzed. This Indicates A Strong Concentration Of Research On Entrepreneurial Orientation In These Countries.

Other Notable Countries Include Germany With 25 Articles, Spain With 24 Articles, Finland With 20 Articles, Australia And France With 17 Articles Each.

These Data Suggest A Geographical Diversity In Research On Entrepreneurial Orientation, But Also A Significant Concentration Of Scientific Production In A Few Key Countries.

However, No Moroccan Studies Were Identified, Which Reinforces Our Motivation To Address The Topic Of Entrepreneurial Orientation In The Specific Context Of Moroccan Smes And To Make An Additional Contribution To The Existing Literature.

3.5. Citation And Co-Citation Analysis

This 2^{ème} Part Of The Analysis Of The Results Presents A Discussion Of The Most Productive Authors In The Field; The Most Cited Articles; The Map Of Citations And Co-Citations As Well As The Main Themes Studied In EO Studies. These Data Represent A Set Of Indicators Of The Field And Can Generate "A Big Picture" Of EO As An Area Of Interest For Our

Research.

3.5.1. Most Cited Articles On The Subject Of Entrepreneurial Orientation

Among The 405 Articles, A Group Of 20 Articles (Table 5) Were Observed To Have Been Cited More Than 100 Times. This Implies The Relevance Of These Studies In Entrepreneurial Orientation Research.

Table 5. List Of The 20 Most Cited Articles In Scopus, Based On A Sample Of 415.

Authors	Titles	Journals	Quote
(Boso Et Al., 2013)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation, Market Orientation, Network Ties, And Performance: Study Of Entrepreneurial Firms In A Developing Economy”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS VENTURING	415
(Anderson & Eshima, 2013)	<i>“The Influence Of Firm Age And Intangible Resources On The Relationship Between Entrepreneurial Orientation And Firm Growth Among Japanese Smes”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS VENTURING	273
(Ferreira Et Al., 2020)	<i>“Dynamic Capabilities, Creativity And Innovation Capability And Their Impact On Competitive Advantage And Firm Performance: The Moderating Role Of Entrepreneurial Orientation”</i>	TECHNOVATION	255
(Singh Et Al., 2021)	<i>“Top Management Knowledge Value, Knowledge Sharing Practices, Open Innovation And Organizational Performance”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	252
(Martin & Javalgi, 2016)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation, Marketing Capabilities, And Performance: The Moderating Role Of Competitive Intensity On Latin American International New Ventures”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	211
(Ciampi Et Al., 2021)	<i>“Exploring The Impact Of Big Data Analytics Capabilities On Business Model</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	190

	<i>Innovation: The Mediating Role Of Entrepreneurial Orientation”</i>		
(Tsai & Yang, 2013)	<i>“Firm Innovativeness And Business Performance: The Joint Moderating Effects Of Market Turbulence And Competition”</i>	INDUSTRIAL MARKETING MANAGEMENT	188
(Shan Et Al., 2016)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation And Performance: Is Innovation Speed A MissingLink?”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	186
(Dai Et Al., 2014)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation And International Scope: The Differential Roles Of Innovativeness, Proactiveness, And Risk- Taking”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS VENTURING	184
(Engelen Et Al., 2014)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation In Turbulent Environments: The Moderating Role Of Absorptive Capacity”</i>	RESEARCH POLICY	161
(Hock-Doepgen Et Al., 2021)	<i>“Knowledge Management Capabilities And Organizational Risk-Taking For Business Model Innovation In Smes”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	148
Ciampi Et Al. (2021)	<i>“Exploring The Impact Of Big Data Analytics Capabilities On Business Model Innovation: The Mediating Role Of Entrepreneurial Orientation”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	190
(Tsai & Yang, 2013)	<i>“Firm Innovativeness And Business Performance: The Joint Moderating Effects Of Market Turbulence And Competition”</i>	INDUSTRIAL MARKETING MANAGEMENT	188
(Shan Et Al., 2016)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation And Performance: Is Innovation Speed A MissingLink?”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS RESEARCH	186

(Dai Et Al., 2014)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation And International Scope: The Differential Roles Of Innovativeness, Proactiveness, And Risk- Taking”</i>	JOURNAL OF BUSINESS VENTURING	184
(Fernández-Mesa & Alegre, 2015)	<i>“Entrepreneurial Orientation And Export Intensity: Examining The Interplay Of Organizational Learning And Innovation”</i>	INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS REVIEW	142

Source: Compiled By Us From The Scopus Database

Among The Most Cited Authors, The Work Of Boso Et Al. (2013) Stands Out With A Total Of 415 Citations, Closely Followed By Anderson & Eshima (2013) With 273 Citations. These Figures Testify To A Significant Recognition On The Part Of The Academic Community Towards These Researchers For Their Major Contribution To Entrepreneurial Orientation. In Addition, Several Other Contributions Also Stand Out, Such As Those By Ferreira Et Al. (2020) With 255 Citations, Singh Et Al. (2021) With 252 Citations, And Martin & Javalgi (2016) With 211 Citations, Highlighting The Diversity Of Work Having A Significant Impact In This Field.

What's More, The Most Cited Studies Were Published Over A Relatively Recent Period, From 2013 To 2021. This Reflects The Continuing Vitality Of Research On Entrepreneurial Orientation And Underlines The Importance Attached To This Topic By The Academic Community.

3.5.2. Map Of Citations And Co-Citations Of Listed References

On The Other Hand, Analysis Of The Citations And Co-Citations Contained In The References Of The 415 Articles In The Sample Has Enabled Us To Identify The Authors Most Cited In Studies On Entrepreneurial Orientation (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Citation And Co-Citation Map Of References Listed In Sample Articles

Source: Compiled By Us Using Vosviewer

The Graph Generated By Vosviewer Clearly Illustrates The Centrality Of Authors Covin, J.G. (1245 Citations), Miller, D. (932), Lumpkin, G.T. (813), Wiklund, J. (761), Zahra, S.A. (734), Rauch, A. (712) And Wales, W.J. (678). This Shows That The Work Of These Authors Is Widely Recognized As An Essential Reference In The Field Of Entrepreneurial Guidance. Consequently, Incorporating These Sources Into Our Research Would Be Extremely Beneficial In Enriching The Literature Review On The Concept Of Entrepreneurial Orientation.

In Addition, The Map Shows That Most Of The Studies Referred To The Theory Of Dynamic Capabilities Developed By Teece Et Al. (1997) And To The Resource Management Theory Developed By Barney (1991). It Would Therefore Make Sense To Integrate These Theories Into Our Research To Formulate Our Research Hypotheses.

Moreover, The Eminent Author Hair JF, Renowned For His Work In The Field Of Structural Equation Analysis, Was Widely Cited. This Suggests That The Majority Of Studies Among The 415 Articles Examined Entrepreneurial Orientation Based On The Structural Equation Approach.

The Map Also Highlights The Contribution Of The Author Podsakoff & Organ (1986) Known For Their Research On The Common Bias Method. This Method Is Often Used To Mitigate The Potential Effects Of Bias Resulting From Unmeasured Or Uncontrolled Variables In A Study. By Incorporating This Method, Entrepreneurial Orientation Researchers Have Sought To Guarantee The Reliability And Validity Of Their Results. Thus, It Would Be Relevant To Incorporate This Approach Into Our Study When Analyzing The Statistical Data.

3.5.3. Main Topics Covered In Studies On Entrepreneurial Orientation

Vosviewer Was Used To Analyze The Main Topics Covered In The 415 Articles In The Sample. An Article Topic Map Was Generated From The Analysis Of Titles And Abstracts, Visualizing The Most Frequent Topics In Entrepreneurial Orientation Research, The Intensity Of Their Occurrence In The Studies, As Well As Related Topics (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Map Of Themes Related To The Entrepreneurial Orientation Study

Source: Compiled By Us Using Vosviewer

As Can Be Seen From The Mapping Of The Topics Dealt With In Relation To Entrepreneurial Orientation, It Is Clear That The Terms "Performance", "Market Orientation" And "Innovation" Have The Highest Incidence And Centrality, Showing That These Topics Are Closely Linked To Entrepreneurial Orientation.

The Term "Performance" (373 Occurrences) Indicates That The Majority Of Studies Focus On The Impact Of EO On Organizational Performance. Next, The Term "Market Orientation" (150 Occurrences) Emerges As The Second Most-Studied Theme In The Context Of EO, Underlining An Interactive Relationship Between These Two Variables. Similarly, The Term "Innovation" (95 Occurrences) Demonstrates That EO Plays A Crucial Role As A Major Antecedent In The Development Of Innovative Activities Within Companies.

The Two Theories "Dynamic Capabilities" (103 Occurrences) And "Resource-Based Management" (82 Occurrences) Were Frequently Used In Studies Of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Reaffirming Our Previous Finding. Indeed, These Two Theories Have Been Widely Mobilized To Frame Hypothetical Relationships Between EO And Other Variables. We Emphasize That We Have Also Used These Two Theories To Support Our Research Hypotheses In This Thesis.

Also Noteworthy Is The Presence Of The Term "Learning Orientation" On The Map, Albeit With A Low Occurrence (24). This Highlights A Gap In The Literature Concerning Interactions Between EO And Learning Orientation. This Observation Motivated Us To Include This Variable In Our Thesis, In Order To Fill This Gap And Deepen Our Understanding Of The Relationship Between Entrepreneurial Orientation And Learning Orientation.

4. Conclusion

In Conclusion, This Study Used A Bibliometric Approach To Explore The Literature On SME Entrepreneurial Orientation. Through This Analysis, We Were Able To Map Trends, Identify The Most Influential Research Works, And Highlight Gaps To Be Filled In This Field. Our Findings Provide Valuable Insights For Researchers And Practitioners Alike, Highlighting The Growing Importance Of Entrepreneurial Orientation In The Operation And Performance Of Smes. In Addition, This Study Highlights The Importance Of Further Research In This Area To Better Understand Entrepreneurial Dynamics And Develop Effective Strategies To Support Entrepreneurship Within Smes. Finally, This Bibliometric Analysis Will Serve As A Solid Basis For Future Research And Contribute To Enriching The Literature On SME Entrepreneurial Orientation.

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